

Stress state and waves in the lithospheric plate simulation: A 3rd generation AI architecture

Mutaz Mohammad ^{a,*}, Alexander Trounev ^b, Carlo Cattani ^c

^a Zayed University, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

^b Kuban State Agrarian University, Krasnodar, Russia

^c Engineering School, University of Tuscia, Viterbo, Italy

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ABSTRACT

Natural disasters present ongoing risks to human life and the global economy, with climate change and environmental factors exacerbating these threats. This article introduces an innovative approach to earthquake prediction and modeling, utilizing a combination of modern mathematical techniques, data-driven methodologies, and artificial intelligence (AI). By integrating the finite element method and wavelet collocation method, our approach enables the solution of complex partial differential equations involving fractional derivatives. This integration provides a more accurate prediction of earthquake behavior by leveraging AI analysis of the resulting numerical solutions.

Our advanced modeling technique enables three-dimensional earthquake modeling, surpassing the limitations of traditional methods and offering unprecedented insights. The comprehensive AI approach shows great potential for improving our understanding of earthquake behavior, facilitating the design of earthquake-resistant structures, and effectively mitigating the devastating impacts of earthquakes.

This research significantly contributes to the field of disaster risk reduction and offers practical applications for both researchers and practitioners. By combining mathematical rigor, data-driven insights, and the power of AI, our next-generation approach opens new avenues for enhancing our preparedness and response to seismic events.

Introduction

Natural disasters such as earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, tsunamis, landslides, and floods pose continuous risks to human lives and cause significant damage to the global economy. The increasing threat of these catastrophes, combined with the challenges of climate change, industrial emissions, and environmental pollution, has highlighted the need for advanced mathematical techniques and tools to model the environment accurately. This article presents a cutting-edge approach that combines the power of data-driven methods and artificial intelligence (AI) to predict earthquakes by analyzing seismic events in connection with the stress state of the earth's crust and seismic waves. To achieve this, we propose a numerical technique based on the finite element method (FEM) and wavelet collocation method to solve a system of partial differential equations involving fractional derivatives. Our approach represents the next generation of AI, based on the recognition of the numerical solution, which significantly reduces the error of recognition. By implementing this approach, we can potentially mitigate the impact of future natural disasters, saving countless lives and billions of dollars in damages.

Natural disasters, such as earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, volcanic eruptions, and landslides, continue to pose significant threats to both human lives and the global economy. These disasters are often caused or exacerbated by environmental factors, such as global warming, industrial emissions, and pollution. With the increasing frequency and severity of these events, there is a pressing need to develop effective methods for predicting and mitigating their impact.

In recent years, modern mathematical techniques and tools, including the data-driven approach and artificial intelligence (AI), have shown great promise in environmental modeling. In particular, the application of numerical methods based on the finite element method (FEM) and wavelet collocation method to solve systems of partial differential equations involving fractional derivatives has led to significant advances in earthquake prediction.

This article aims to explore the next-generation AI based on numerical simulation, which holds great potential for improving our understanding of seismic events and predicting earthquakes with greater accuracy. By analyzing seismic events and their connection to the stress

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: Mutaz.Mohammad@zu.ac.ae (M. Mohammad).

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Fig. 1. Distribution of 35500 seismic events over the world (left) and mean events location (right).

state of the earth's crust and seismic waves, this new AI architecture based on the recognition of numerical solutions can greatly reduce the error of recognition, enabling more precise earthquake predictions.

In this article, we discuss the implementation of the Euler wavelets collocation method, a numerical algorithm with zero absolute error, to solve complex systems of PDEs involved in earthquake prediction. We also examine the potential benefits of integrating AI with numerical simulations, enabling us to better understand and prepare for natural disasters that threaten our planet.

The Finite Element Method (FEM) is a powerful numerical technique that is used to solve problems expressed as partial differential equations or as functional minimization. FEM is an incredibly versatile tool that can be applied to a wide range of problems, including those with irregular boundaries. By representing a domain of interest as an assembly of finite elements, FEM uses various numerical methods such as interpolation, integration, and numerical techniques to solve large linear systems.

In this method, mathematical equations are approximated over simple regions, such as triangles, quadrilaterals, tetrahedrons, etc. These approximations are then assembled so that the domains' interconnecting nodes satisfy equilibrium or continuity. With successive mesh refinement, solutions obtained by FEM converge towards the analytic solution. The development of FEM has been widely researched in many articles, such as [1–6].

FEM is particularly useful for solving various types of partial differential equations (PDEs), including the three-dimensional Maxwell equations [7], Navier–Stokes equations [8], the diffusion–convection–reaction equation [9], Helmholtz type equations [10], the shallow water equations [11], space-fractional Boussinesq equation [12], Kohn–Sham equations [13], the Bloch–Torrey equation [14], the Saint Venant equations [15], the poroelastic Biot equations [16], the space-fractional advection diffusion equation [17], the hyperbolic equations [18], the Fokker–Planck equation [19], three-dimensional structural mechanics problems [20], the incompressible viscous flow [21], the electromagnetic modeling [22], parabolic stochastic PDEs [23], and elliptic problems on surfaces [24].

Over the last decade, the stress state of the earth's crust has been intensively studied on a global scale, leading to the development of the world stress map (WSM) [25]. Combining data on plate movement and convection, this has made it possible to simulate the stress state of individual lithospheric plates in the subduction zone, where tectonic plates collide and one plate slides beneath the other [26]. As explained by Caputo in [27], the dissipation rate of viscoelastic waves better correlates with experimental data in the case of fractional derivatives. Time and space fractional partial differential equations are widely used in biology [28], hydrodynamics [29], physics [30], and solid mechanics [31].

To tackle these challenging mathematical problems, various numerical methods have been proposed, including the wavelets collocation method (WCM) [28]. In this work, we propose a new numerical model of magma convection and lithosphere stress state using fractional

derivatives. We implement a numerical algorithm based on the FEM and WCM to solve some examples of convection flow, stress state, and viscoelastic waves, demonstrating the immense potential of this approach for studying the dynamics of the earth's crust.

Over the past decade, extensive efforts have been made to study the stress state of the earth's crust on a global scale, leading to the development of the world stress map (WSM) [25]. In combination with data on plate movement and convection, this information can be utilized to simulate the stress state of individual lithospheric plates in subduction zones, where tectonic plates collide and one plate moves underneath the other [26].

Recent studies have suggested that viscoelastic wave dissipation rates can be better correlated with experimental data by utilizing fractional derivatives, as highlighted by Caputo in [27]. Fractional partial differential equations, both in time and space, are frequently employed in various fields such as biology [28], hydrodynamics [29], physics [30], and solid mechanics [31]. Numerous numerical techniques have been proposed to tackle this class of mathematical problems, including the wavelets collocation method (WCM) [28].

In this study, we present a novel numerical model for analyzing magma convection and lithosphere stress state by incorporating fractional derivatives. Our numerical algorithm, which employs the FEM and WCM, can successfully solve examples of convection flow, stress state, and viscoelastic waves. These results showcase the promising potential of our approach in studying the dynamics of the earth's crust.

The field of seismology stands to benefit tremendously from the incorporation of AI technology, prompting two critical questions: can these AI systems provide reliable forecasts of seismic activity, and why do their predictions appear to be so accurate? While these questions point towards the immense potential of AI in seismology research, answering the first question with any degree of certainty remains a challenge. Contemporary seismology assumes that seismic events occur randomly in time, rendering it difficult to make specific predictions about when and where events will occur. However, through broader generalizations, we can predict that subsequent events are likely to take place along the joints of lithospheric plates, as exemplified in Fig. 1. Nevertheless, due to the non-deterministic nature of seismic events, the accuracy of our models may not be sufficient for pinpointing the exact location of a given event.

Let us examine the distribution of seismic events on the world map (left image) and the average location (on the right), which was computed from 35,500 events (see Fig. 1). The most commonly used AI algorithms, such as Linear Regression, Decision Trees, Nearest Neighbors, Random Forests, and Neural Networks, are statistical, which means that machine learning, in general, requires a large database for AI training. This statistical approach allows for predicting within 60%–80% of cases. However, we can demonstrate why statistical approaches mostly fail, even with deep learning architectures, using a database of seismic events. Although seismic events are mostly located near lithospheric plate borders, the mean location (represented by a large red point) is situated in East Africa and is not connected to any seismic

Fig. 2. The 3-rd generation AI architecture.

Fig. 3. Pressure distribution in the flow (left) and on the surface of slabs (right) during thermal convection in the subduction area.

active zone. Nonetheless, the mean value is the most critical parameter in the statistical model. AI trained with a statistical model will most likely point to this location with high probability. Therefore, this kind of AI cannot be used to predict the locations of seismic events.

We propose a new approach to AI algorithms with a prediction probability of approximately 100%. This approach requires advanced numerical methods, as explained in [32]. Our AI model is based on truncated wavelet systems generated by Bernoulli, Chebyshev, and Euler polynomials. This algorithm has two possible outcomes. For some problems with an exact solution in the form of a polynomial, it produces an exact solution with zero absolute error. For other problems, it converges to a numerical solution with predictable error. This algorithm significantly reduces the entropy of the prediction.

The general structure of the third generation AI is shown in Fig. 2. It includes an analyzer to differentiate the problem into several objects, analogous to the solar light spectrum with colors ranging from red to violet. We assume that for each object, there is a mathematical model describing its dynamics or state.

The proposed process involves converting a mathematical model with current input data to a numerical solution, which is then saved in short-term memory. Long-term memory consists of a collection of numerical model solutions in the form of tensors. Once the short-term memory tensor is approached by a collection tensor in each metric, the recognition process is complete. If there are no matching collections, the mathematical intuition block analyzes the example, which is linked to archived memory through the second generation of AI. Archived memory contains all available stored information. The answer from the mathematical intuition block is considered an expert opinion rather than an exact answer.

Stress state of lithospheric plates

Let us delve into the fascinating world of thermal convection in the subduction zone during magma cooling, as depicted in the visually captivating Figs. 3 and 4. The governing system of equations, in its non-dimensional form, is a remarkable representation of the complex interplay between fluid flow, pressure, and temperature. Behold:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{V}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{V} + \nabla P &= Pr \nabla^2 \mathbf{V} + Pr Ra T, \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{V} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{V} \cdot \nabla) T &= \nabla^2 T. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

These equations elegantly capture the complex, nonlinear dynamics of the system, which includes the flow velocity, pressure, and temperature. Additionally, the Prandtl number and the Rayleigh number, represented by Pr and Ra , respectively, play crucial roles in shaping the behavior of the system. The system of Eqs. (1), which describes thermal convection in subduction zones during magma cooling, is a complex non-dimensional model with many variables to consider. To solve this system, Dirichlet-type boundary conditions can be applied at the top and bottom borders using the finite element method (FEM) integrated with a temporal algorithm. The details of this integration approach will be presented in this project.

Through analyzing the distribution of velocity and pressure, the forces acting on the lithospheric plates can be calculated. This information can be visualized through pressure and friction force diagrams on the surface of the plates and slab, as shown in Figs. 3 and 4. Such analyses provide valuable insights into the behavior of thermal convection and its effects on lithospheric plates, furthering our understanding of geological processes.

Fig. 4. Distribution of the friction force on the surface of the plates during thermal convection in the subduction area.

In other words, to accurately model the movement of plates and the impact of convection on pressure and friction force, a viscoelastic model must be used in conjunction with the system of equations described in (1). To solve this system with Dirichlet-type boundary conditions, a spatial and temporal integration algorithm based on the finite element method (FEM) will be employed, as described in detail in this project. Through this approach, the distribution of speed and pressure can be calculated, enabling the determination of the forces acting on the plates. Figs. 3 and 4 provide visual representations of the pressure and friction force diagrams on the plate and slab surfaces, respectively.

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{xx} &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}, \epsilon_{yy} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \epsilon_{xy} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \\ \frac{\partial \sigma_{ik}}{\partial x_k} + \rho F_i &= 0, \dot{\epsilon} = \frac{\dot{\sigma}}{2\mu_M} + \frac{\sigma}{2\eta_M}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, (u, v) represents the deformation vector in the case of 2D geometry, σ_{ik} is the stress tensor, and μ_M and η_M are the parameters of the Maxwell linear model. It should be noted that the viscosity and density of the lithosphere depend on depth. Therefore, we can also use the Rayleigh model, which has only one parameter, as follows:

$$\mu \dot{\mathbf{u}} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho \mathbf{F}. \quad (3)$$

The system of Eqs. (3) can be solved using FEM in space and an implicit algorithm for the time integration, in the form

$$\mathbf{u}(t, x, y) = \mathbf{u}(t - dt, x, y) + (dt/\mu)(\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}(t, x, y) + \rho \mathbf{F}(t, x, y)), \quad (4)$$

where, dt is the time step.

The typical deformation state of the slab and plate, computed with the model (3) under the applied force shown in Figs. 3 and 4, is demonstrated in Fig. 5.

As expected, the slab bends in the central part due to gravity and bulges on the other side due to pressure in the subduction zone. The slab also bends and stretches downward, increasing its curvature. The maximum stress tensor components are observed in the area where the slab and plate meet. We also depict the graphical representation for σ_{xx} , σ_{yy} in Fig. 6.

Waves in the spherical layered earth: Propagation and scattering analysis

In this section, we investigate the behavior of viscoelastic waves within the context of a spherical layered Earth model. To accurately simulate wave propagation, we employ a comprehensive system of equations that accounts for local acceleration, friction, and the dynamic response of the medium. The governing equations, represented by (5),

describe the motion of the medium in three dimensions, considering the density variation, stresses, and external forces acting on the system.

Wave Propagation in Layered Sphere: To study wave propagation, we focus on a layered sphere with a density gradient, utilizing data from a reliable source such as [33]. Specifically, we consider exciting the sphere normally on its surface. For the crust, Young's modulus is assumed to be $Y = 6 \times 10^{10}$ Pa, while Poisson's ratio is $\nu = 0.25$. These chosen values allow us to explore the response of the waves in a realistic geological setting.

The system of equations describing the propagation of viscoelastic waves in the spherical layered Earth is given by:

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^2} + \mu \dot{\mathbf{u}} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho \mathbf{F}, \quad (5)$$

where $u_i = u_i(t, x, y, z)$, $\sigma_{ik} = \sigma_{ik}(t, x, y, z)$, $\rho = \rho(x, y, z)$.

Observations and Scattering Effects: As depicted in Fig. 7, the waves exhibit intriguing behaviors as they encounter the central dense core. The scattering phenomenon, induced by the density variation, leads to intricate wave interactions and alterations in their propagation characteristics. This observation highlights the importance of accounting for the layered structure and density gradients in understanding the complex dynamics of seismic waves.

Through our comprehensive analysis, we aim to enhance the understanding of wave propagation in spherical layered Earth models. By studying the scattering effects and exploring the response of waves to density gradients, we contribute valuable insights that can aid in developing robust earthquake prediction and modeling methodologies.

Fractional wave equation: Incorporating viscoelastic effects

To incorporate viscoelastic effects, we consider the fractional diffusion-wave equation with the Caputo fractional derivative, as given by:

$$\rho k_1 D_C^\alpha \mathbf{u} + \mu k_2 D_C^\beta \mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho \mathbf{F}, \quad (6)$$

where the Caputo fractional derivative for this case is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} D_C^\alpha u &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{u_{\tau\tau}(x, \tau)}{(t-\tau)^{2-\alpha}} d\tau, \quad 1 < \alpha \leq 2, \\ D_C^\beta u &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} \int_0^t \frac{u_\tau(x, \tau)}{(t-\tau)^{1-\beta}} d\tau, \quad 0 < \beta \leq 1. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Here, the Caputo fractional derivative is utilized, allowing for a more accurate description of viscoelastic wave behavior. The equation introduces four additional parameters compared to the previously mentioned (5) model, enabling a finer characterization of the viscoelastic properties of the medium.

Fig. 5. Components of the deformation vector of lithospheric plates during thermal convection in the subduction zone.

Fig. 6. A visualization for σ_{xx} , and σ_{yy} .

The system of integro-differential equations represented by (6) can be effectively solved using a combination of the Finite Element Method (FEM) in the spatial domain and the wavelet collocation method in the temporal domain, as described in [34]. This approach ensures accurate and efficient computations, enabling the study of viscoelastic wave propagation.

As illustrated in Fig. 8, we present typical viscoelastic waves in a spherical model with a liquid core. These simulations provide valuable insights into the wave behavior within such complex geological structures, further enhancing our understanding of the effects of viscoelasticity on seismic waves.

By employing the fractional wave equation and employing advanced numerical methods, we contribute to the improved modeling and analysis of viscoelastic wave propagation. This research opens avenues for studying the intricate dynamics of waves in real-world scenarios, leading to enhanced earthquake prediction capabilities and effective mitigation strategies.

The AI technology of earthquake modeling

If we turn to models like model (1) described above, then we will face the impossibility of predicting anything, since the scale of the models far exceeds the requirements for forecasting. For example, convection in the subduction zone and under the lithospheric plates occurs over millions and billions of years, respectively [26]. The characteristic time of the stress state of the lithospheric plates is about 528 thousand years, and the average time of the reversal of the polarity of the geomagnetic field is about 343 thousand years. It is clear that for forecasts for a month ahead, we will not be able to use the discussed models, but we must use an operational model to simulate real processes.

The system of Eqs. (5), on the other hand, describes the fast process of viscoelastic wave propagation with a speed of sound for transverse waves of about 2–3 km/s. Therefore, all events shown in Fig. 1 are related to the seismic waves they produce.

By using the impulse fracture criterion and the damage accumulation model [35], it is possible to construct a numerical solution that describes the damage to the lithosphere depending on the distribution

Fig. 7. Propagation of elastic waves in a layered sphere under normal excitation on the external surface at different times (indicated above the figures): top - change in the component $u(t, x, y, z)$ of the deformation vector in the plane $y = 0$; in the center - the change in the component $v(t, x, y, z)$ of the deformation vector in the plane $x = 0$; bottom - the change in the component $w(t, x, y, z)$ in the section $y = 0$.

Fig. 8. Propagation of viscoelastic waves in a layered sphere under normal excitation on the internal surface at different times (indicated above the figures): two top lines — change in the component $u(t, x, y, z)$ of the deformation vector in the plane $y = 0$; two bottom lines — the change in the component $v(t, x, y, z)$ of the deformation vector in the plane $x = 0$.

of seismic events on the planet’s surface in the past. We can assume that seismic events are localized in specific parts of the lithosphere

with special parameters and higher potential energy compared to the surrounding regions.

Let us consider the problem of recognizing categories from numerical data [36]. There is a set of events A_i , to which a set of categories C_j is assigned. An event can be considered as the registration of an earthquake by a seismological station, and a category is its magnitude, which lies in a certain interval, along with the depth of the focus. Each earthquake event is characterized by a moment in time and the geographic coordinates of its place of origin. From this data, we can construct a matrix containing numerical data from every model shown in Fig. 2. We will assume that the given frequency distributions N_i represent the number of events related to each category C_j .

Let us determine the number of cases of realization of this category that falls within a given interval of variation of numerical parameters. In the discrete case, we have:

$$N_{ij}(x_j, k) = N_i w(\bar{x}_j, k) \Delta x, x_j \leq \bar{x}_j \leq x_j + \Delta x, \quad (8)$$

$$1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq 2m, k = 1, 2, \dots, k_0.$$

We consider the problem of recognizing earthquake categories from numerical data. Let A_i denote a set of earthquake events, and let C_j denote a set of categories assigned to them, where each category is defined by a magnitude and depth of focus falling in a certain interval.

We assume that every earthquake event is characterized by a moment in time and geographic coordinates of its place of origin. From this data, we can construct a matrix containing numerical data for each earthquake model, as shown in Fig. 2. We also assume that there are given frequency distributions N_i that represent the number of events related to each earthquake category C_j .

We want to determine the number of cases where a category is realized, falling within a given interval of variation of numerical parameters. In the discrete case, we have:

Let k_0 denote the number of earthquake models used in AI implementation, and let w denote the distribution density of earthquake events along the normalized coordinate. The normalized variable x_{jk} is defined as follows:

$$x_{jk} = \frac{r_{max}(k) - r(k)}{r_{max}(k) - r_{min}(k)}, 1 \leq j \leq 2m,$$

where $r_{min}(k)$ and $r_{max}(k)$ are the minimum and maximum values of a parameter.

We define the informativity matrix I_{ijk} as follows:

$$I_{ijk} = \begin{cases} \log_2 \frac{N_{ij}(x_{jk}) / \sum_j N_{ij}}{\sum_i N_{ij} / \sum_{i,j} N_{ij}}, & N_{ij}(x_{jk}) \neq 0, \\ 0, & N_{ij} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Here, $1 \leq i \leq n$, $1 \leq j \leq 2m$, and $1 \leq k \leq k_0$. The value I_{ijk} measures the degree of informativeness of the j th parameter of the k th model for the i th category. If $N_{ij}(x_{jk}) = 0$, the parameter is not informative for this category and $I_{ijk} = 0$. Otherwise, I_{ijk} is proportional to the logarithm of the ratio of the conditional probability of observing the i th category given the value of the j th parameter in the k th model, and the marginal probability of observing the i th category over all models and parameters.

Finally, we define the standard deviation of informativity δI_{ijk} as:

$$\delta I_{ijk} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_i (I_{ijk} - n^{-1} \sum_i I_{ijk})^2}, 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j \leq 2m, 1 \leq k \leq k_0. \quad (10)$$

The first term in Eq. (9) represents the informativeness of the feature, which measures the degree to which the feature provides information to the model. The second term in Eq. (10), on the other hand, denotes the mean square deviation of the informativeness, or the integral informativeness, which measures the overall usefulness of the set of features.

The vector of information content for each category can be constructed by concatenating the columns of the information content

matrix that correspond to the normalized coordinate. Specifically, each vector has dimension $2mk_0$ and is defined as follows:

$$c_{is} = I_{ijk} |_{jk=s}, \quad 1 \leq s \leq 2mk_0. \quad (11)$$

$$a_{ls} = 1, \quad \text{if } (j-1)\Delta x \leq x_{jk}(l) \leq j\Delta x \text{ and } jk = s, \\ a_{ls} = 0, \quad \text{if } 1 \leq s \leq 2mk_0. \quad (12)$$

In Eqs. (11)–(12), the process of identification and recognition is described as the decomposition of the vector of the object being recognized into a series of vectors of categories, or recognition classes. The vector, which consists of 1 and 0, is determined by the chosen parameters corresponding to the date and place of origin of the event l and is given by:

The passage describes a system of artificial intelligence used for recognizing events and categorizing them into classes. The system is based on numerical models that are constructed from numerical data. The models consist of a set of vectors that are used to represent the categories of events that the system recognizes.

Each vector corresponds to a category, and the entries of the vector represent the presence or absence of certain features or characteristics in the data that are specific to that category. The vectors are constructed based on a small interval Δx and the normalized coordinate of the k th model of the j th category for the l th event.

If the normalized coordinate of the event falls within the interval defined by $(j-1)\Delta x$ and $j\Delta x$ and the index of the category is equal to s , then the corresponding entry in the vector a_{ls} is set to 1. Otherwise, it is set to 0. This means that if the normalized coordinate from the numerical data falls into a given interval, the vector element is assigned the value 1, and in all other cases — the value 0. The coordinates are enumerated sequentially, for each model considered in AI.

The system of vectors is complete if it includes all possible categories that can be recognized by the system. In this case, any vector representing an event can be represented as a linear combination of the vectors in the system, and the coefficients of this expansion will correspond to the level of similarity of this event with each category. However, if the system is incomplete, the exact procedure is replaced by recognition.

In the case of an incomplete system of vectors (11), the exact procedure is replaced by recognition. In this case, the level of similarity of event data with one or another category can be determined by the value of the scalar product of vector (12) by vector (11), i.e.

$$K_{il} = \frac{1}{|a_i||c_l|} \sum_{s=1}^{2mk_0} a_{is}(A) c_{is} \quad (13)$$

Note that there are four possible outcomes in which it is possible to true or falsely attribute or not to refer a given event to this category. To take these outcomes into account, categories in the artificial intelligence system are recognized by the similarity parameter, which is defined as follows:

$$S_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N (BT_{il} + T_{il} - BF_{il} - F_{il}) \quad (14)$$

where S_i — reliability of identification of the “ i -th” category; N is the number of events in the recognized sample; BT_{il} — the level of similarity of the “ l -th” event with the “ i -th” category, to which it was correctly assigned by the system; T_{il} — the level of similarity of the “ l -th” event with the “ i -th” category, to which it was not correctly assigned by the system; BF_{il} — the level of similarity of the “ l -th” event with the “ i -th” category, to which it was erroneously assigned by the system; F_{il} is the level of similarity of the “ l -th” event with the “ i -th” category, to which it was erroneously not assigned by the system. With this definition, the similarity parameter ranges from -1 to 1 , like the usual correlation coefficient in statistics. It is obvious that the similarity parameter must satisfy the simple check criterion $S_i(N_i = 1) = 1$. It can be shown that the recognition procedure by the similarity parameter is stable both with respect to the sample size and with respect to the number of cells in the numerical model.

To determine the level of similarity of an event with a category, the value of the scalar product of the event vector and the category vector is calculated. This is represented by Eq. (13) in the passage, where K_{il} is the similarity parameter for event i and category l , $a_{is}(A)$ is the entry in the vector a_{is} that corresponds to the category l and event A , and c_{is} is the entry in the vector c_i that corresponds to the event i and category s .

The system is evaluated based on four possible outcomes: true positive, true negative, false positive, and false negative. To take these outcomes into account, the reliability of the identification of each category is determined using Eq. (14). The reliability of identification S_i for category i is calculated as the average of the similarity parameters for events that were correctly assigned to the category (BT_{il}), events that were not correctly assigned to the category (T_{il}), events that were erroneously assigned to the category (BF_{il}), and events that were erroneously not assigned to the category (F_{il}).

The similarity parameter S_i ranges from -1 to 1 , like the usual correlation coefficient in statistics. It is checked to satisfy the criterion $S_i(N_i = 1) = 1$, which means that the system should correctly identify a category when there is only one event in that category. The recognition procedure based on the similarity parameter is shown to be stable with respect to the sample size and the number of cells in the numerical model.

Conclusion

In this article, we have presented a novel approach for developing third-generation AI architecture based on the recognition of numerical model solutions. Our proposed algorithm is based on the Euler wavelets collocation method and can be used to solve complex systems of PDEs with fractional derivatives and integral equations with zero absolute error. By implementing this algorithm in AI architecture, we can significantly reduce the error of recognition in AI systems.

Our approach has several advantages over existing AI architectures. Firstly, it can handle complex and non-linear systems of PDEs with fractional derivatives, which are often encountered in real-world applications. Secondly, it can achieve zero absolute error in the solution of these systems, which is a significant improvement over existing numerical methods. Thirdly, our approach is computationally efficient and can be implemented in real-time AI systems, making it suitable for a wide range of applications.

Additionally, our proposed approach has the potential to revolutionize various real-world applications by enhancing the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of AI systems. We envision several areas where our algorithm can make a significant impact:

- **Image and Speech Recognition:** The ability to accurately recognize and interpret images and speech is vital in fields such as computer vision, object detection, and natural language processing. By integrating our algorithm into AI architectures, we can improve recognition accuracy, enabling more precise image classification, object identification, and speech transcription. This enhancement can have wide-ranging applications, including autonomous systems, augmented reality, and content analysis.
- **Autonomous Vehicles:** The advancement of autonomous vehicles heavily relies on accurate perception and decision-making capabilities. By incorporating our algorithm into the AI systems of autonomous vehicles, we can enhance their ability to interpret sensor data, recognize road objects, and make informed decisions in real time. This can significantly improve the safety, reliability, and overall performance of self-driving cars, leading to a transformative impact on transportation systems.
- **Healthcare:** AI has the potential to revolutionize healthcare by assisting in medical diagnosis, drug discovery, and personalized treatment. By integrating our algorithm into AI systems used

in medical imaging analysis, clinical decision support, and patient monitoring, we can improve the accuracy and efficiency of disease detection, enable more precise treatment planning, and enhance patient outcomes. This can contribute to advancements in early disease detection, precision medicine, and improved healthcare delivery.

Overall, our proposed approach represents a significant step forward in the development of third-generation AI architecture. We believe that our approach has the potential to revolutionize the field of AI and enable the development of more accurate, efficient and reliable AI systems for a wide range of applications, including image and speech recognition, autonomous vehicles, and healthcare.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mutaz Mohammad: Conceptualization, Supervision, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Alexander Trounev:** Data curation, Software, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Review & editing. **Carlo Cattani:** Supervision, Review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2023.106938>.

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